

A STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AND GENERAL HEALTH AMONG GOVERNMENT SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

Ms.G Lourds Shammine
Ph.D Research Scholar,
Department of Social Work,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

&
Dr.M.Punitha
Head & Professor, Department of Social Work,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Abstract

Education helps in developing all the aspects of individuality namely physical, mental, moral, emotional, social and spiritual as it enables to meet their basic needs and necessities of life. Life skills are competency for adaptive and positive performance that enables persons to deal efficiently with the challenges and demands of daily life activities WHO, 1997. Life skill education aims to give adolescent students with the approach to make strong choices that give to a consequential life. Life skills are the skills that help to endorse mental well-being and ability in adolescent's student as they face the reality of life. Life skills assist the adolescent's students to acquire positive measures to keep themselves uphold meaningful and healthy social connection. It assists an integrated and complete progress of persons to perform successfully as social beings. Life skills are also being able to create fruitful interpersonal relations with others. Developing life skills help adolescent's students to translating attitude, general health, values and knowledge into strong conduct that make their life fruitful. Life skill education is a worth new plan which aims to afford students with approach to make strong choice that give to an important life. Life skills also help adolescents to acquire down with other people and regulate with their surroundings and make accountable conclusion. This study respondents a descriptive research design and multistage sampling technique. A sample size of 534 people was collected using a questionnaire.

Key Words: Life skills, General Health.

INTRODUCTION

Life skills help adolescents to recognize their self and to evaluate their abilities, general health areas and skills of improvement. Life skills education is aimed at facilitating the development of psychosocial skills that are required to deal with the demands and challenges of everyday life. It includes the application of life skills in the context of specific risk situations and in situations where children and adolescents need to be empowered to promote and protect their rights. Adolescence is a period of experimenting, experiencing and expanding. Adolescents need help and guidance in decision-making, problem solving, critical thinking, developing interpersonal skills, self-awareness, empathy, coping with stress, academic self efficacy, general health and managing emotions. The rebelliousness and dislike for parental intrusion usually keeps parents at bay because teenagers do not relish the idea of help and guidance from parents. However, this may not always be so. Beneath frequent violent outbursts, sudden mood swings and related interpersonal problems of an adolescent, there may be a person crying out for professional help. All adolescents need support and guidance. When parents find it difficult to handle signs of trouble, professional help should be sought at the earliest.

DEFINITION

LIFE SKILLS

Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable the individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life.

Described in this way, skills that can be said to be life skills are innumerable, and the nature and definition of life skills are likely to differ across cultures and settings. However, analysis of the life skills field suggests that there is a core set of skills that are at the heart of skills-based initiatives for the promotion of the health and well-being of children and adolescents.

GENERAL HEALTH

General health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. The importance of maintaining our health and wellbeing throughout your lifetime by incorporating exercise, diet, preventative health checks, sleep management,

managing mental health issues, finding ways to relax and unwind are all important aspects of our health and wellbeing.

Mental health is an integral and essential component of health. The WHO constitution states: "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." An important implication of this definition is that mental health is more than just the absence of mental disorders or disabilities.

According to the World Health Organization statistics, 12% of illnesses across the world are due to mental health problems or general health. Sixty percent of health problems in middle aged people are related to mental disorders.

The World Health Organization describes the leading health-related problems in the age group 10 – 19 years to include:

- Early pregnancy and childbirth
- HIV
- Other infectious diseases
- Mental health problems including depression and suicide
- Violence
- Alcohol and other drugs
- Injuries both unintentional and self-injury
- Sexual health / Infectious diseases
- Malnutrition and obesity
- Exercise and Nutrition
- Tobacco use
- Rights of adolescents
- Adolescent and young adult oncology

Young people often lack awareness of the risks of harm associated with certain behaviors or may overestimate the risks of some behaviors while underestimating the risks of others. They may be in the process of developing protective skills and behaviors or may lack knowledge about how and where to seek help for their health concerns. By intervening at this early life stage many chronic conditions later in life can be prevented.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kaur (2021) investigate the effect of life skills training on the suicidal behavior of adolescents. The study employs a quasi-experimental research design. The sample comprised of 970 adolescents studying in the ninth grade. The study was carried out in three phases. Life skills training program was conducted in thirty sessions within the school premises. For each life skill training program, sessions were activity-based and participatory. The techniques used to impart training were role play, small group activities, lectures and group discussions. The results show a significant detrimental effect of life skills training on suicidal behavior of adolescents. Life skills training were effective in reducing suicidal behavior among adolescents.

Anand, S.P. (1989) studied general health of high school students. Problem: The general health of class X students in the age group 14-15 years age was investigated. Objective: To study the general health of high school students. Methodology: A sample of 262 high school students (169 boys and 93 girls) participated in the study. A Likert-type general health scale developed by the author was used. Correlation and Chi- square were used for data analysis. Findings: The general health of adolescents, their academic achievement and the educational and occupational status of parents were positively related.

Mostafa Jafari and Shahidi (1987) conducted a research to compare the characteristics of assertiveness, locus of control and general health among young drug dependent patients in Iran. Results showed that there were significant differences among the three groups. It was found that participants in the non addictive group were more assertive and more internal in their locus of control and had higher GHQ scores than the other two groups. The participants in the prison group reported less assertiveness and lower GHQ scores than the non addictive group and their locus of control was more external.

Methodology of the Study

Objective of the Study

- To study the personal profile of the respondents.
- To assess the level of life skills and general health among government school going adolescent.
- To investigate the influence of personal factors on life skills and general health among government school going adolescent.

- To study the relation between life skills and general health among government school going adolescent.
- To examine life skills and general health as significant predictors among government school going adolescent.

Research design: The researcher followed descriptive research design for the study.

Universe of the study: The aggregate of all the units pertaining to the study is called the population or the universe. Researcher selected the respondents of “**GOVERNMENT SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT**” as the universe of the study. The universe size was found to be 534 Government school going adolescent which includes 9th, 10th, 11th and 12th students.

Sampling: 534 government school going adolescent were selected for data collection. The probability sampling technique used for this study is multistage sampling.

Tools for data collection: Personal Profile:

The personal profile of the respondents constitutes a total of 15 questions such as Age, Gender, Class, Type of family, Locality, Father occupation, Total monthly income and the Religion, etc.

Life Skills Assessment Scale was profound by A.Radhakrishnan Nair, R.Subasree & Sunitha Rajan (2010). This schedule has 100 statements rated on a 5 point scale and a reliability of =.891. The items include all relevant components of 1-Always true of me, 2- Very true of me, 3-Sometimes true of me, 4- Occasionally true of me and 5-Not at all true of me.

General Health scale was profound by **Goldberg & Blackwell(1970)**. It consists of 12 questions measured in a 4-point scale in which items rated on a reliability of 0.754. The items include all relevant components of 4-Better than usual, 3- Same as usual, 2- Less than usual and 1- Much less than usual.

The statistical tools applied by the researcher are Percentage Analysis, Chi-square, T-test and ANOVA.

Finds of the Study

Factors	MEDIUM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age	19-21yrs	191	35.8
Gender	Male	304	56.9
Class	Upper class	219	41
Locality	Semi urban	243	45.5
Family type	Nuclear family	336	62.9
Father's education	Primary	132	24.7
Fathers' occupation	Daily Wages	132	24.7
Mother's education	Secondary	118	22.1
Mother's occupation	Others	141	26.4
Total Monthly Income	Below Rs.15,000	217	40.6
Religion	Hindu	315	59.0
Caste	MBC	138	25.8
Birth order	One	196	36.7
Medium of study	Tamil	348	65.2
Hobbies	Playing Games	145	27.2

Personal Profile of the Respondents

- Less than half(**35.8%**) of the respondents belong to the age group 19- 21 yrs.
- More than half(**56.9%**) of the respondents are male.
- Less than half (**41%**)of the total respondents are in the upper class.
- Less than half (**45.5%**) of the respondent's locality is semi urban.
- Majority (**62.9 %**) of respondents are residing in nuclear family.
- Nearly (**24.7%**) of the respondent's fathers education level is primary.
- Nearly (**24.7 %**) of the respondent's father's occupation is daily wages.
- Nearly (**22.1%**) of the respondent's mother's education level issecondary.

- Nearly **(26.4%)** of the respondent's mother's occupation is others.
- Less than half **(40.6 %)** of the respondent's family income per month is below Rs.15,000.
- Nearly **(59 %)** of the respondents are Hindus.
- Nearly **(25.8 %)** of the respondent's caste is FC.
- Less than half **(36.7%)** of the respondents birth order is one.
- Majority **(65.2%)** of the respondent's medium of study is Tamil.
- Less than half **(27.2%)** of the respondent's hobby is playing games.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

LIFE SKILLS LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS

S. No	Life skills	Number of Respondents	Percentage%
1	High (173-500)	085	15.9
2	Moderate (144-240)	388	72.7
3	Low (100-143)	061	11.4
TOTAL		534	100

The above table highlights the life skills level of the respondents. It is understood from the above table that 72.7 percent of the respondents have moderate level of life skills, 15.9 percent of the respondents have high level of life skills and 11.4 percent of the respondents have low level of life skills. Life skills help adolescents make informed decisions, communicate effectively, develop coping and management skills to lead a healthy and productive life. Prajina and Premsingh (2015) found that the school going adolescent who have possessed moderate life skills have medium level percentages in academic scores.

INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL PROFILE AND LIFE SKILLS OF THE RSPONDENTS

S.NO	PERSONAL VARIABLES	TEST APPLIED	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
1	Age	Z	*
2	Gender	F	*
3	Class	Z	NS
4	Locality	Z	*
5	Type of Family	F	*
6	Fathers Education	Z	NS
7	Fathers Occupation	Z	*
8	Mothers Education	Z	NS
9	Mothers Occupation	Z	*
10	Total Monthly Income	Z	*
11	Religion	Z	*
12	Caste	Z	NS
13	Birth Order	Z	*
14	Medium of Study	Z	*
15	Hobbies	Z	*

**INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL PROFILE AND GENERAL HEALTH OF THE
RSPONDENTS**

S.NO	PERSONAL VARIABLES	TEST APPLIED	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
1	Age	Z	*
2	Gender	F	*
3	Class	Z	*
4	Locality	Z	*
5	Type of Family	F	NS
6	Fathers Education	Z	NS
7	Fathers Occupation	Z	*
8	Mothers Education	Z	NS
9	Mothers Occupation	Z	*
10	Total Monthly Income	Z	*
11	Religion	Z	*
12	Caste	Z	*
13	Birth Order	Z	*
14	Medium of Study	Z	*
15	Hobbies	Z	*

SUGGESTIONS

- ❖ Most of the students are interested in getting some life skill training through instructional manuals or materials for continuous learning to enhance their skills and competencies.
- ❖ Since life skills are very important for every student they are expecting to organize the program in different periods to get more experienced in every skill.
- ❖ The institution has to take necessary steps to encourage the students to be more attentive in every session with the help of effective resource person or trainers.

- ❖ It is suggested that initiating the follow - up and monitoring activities after completion of every life skill training program, both the institution and student can be benefited.
- ❖ Ensuring nutritional diet and daily exercise can help the adolescents to deal with malnutrition and obesity.
- ❖ Adolescent health check up has become essential today as it evaluates the teenagers physical as well as mental health and they can get necessary guidance to stay healthy.
- ❖ Parents should set realistic goals and aspirations for female children to build their abilities, competence and confidence in school activities.
- ❖ Government (federal, state and local government areas) should give more priority to girl's education by providing friendly school environment to facilitate teaching and learning activities.
- ❖ The education administration and curriculum wing may review the courses of secondary classes and make them interesting for the students as much as possible.
- ❖ Teachers and parents need to be aware of the students about their strengths and academic goals, make them think that what will be their plan and guide them accordingly.
- ❖ As your teenager enters adolescence it is important to be aware of the health risks they face. Common adolescent health problems include obesity, eating disorders, sexually transmitted diseases and mental health issues.
- ❖ To ensure your teen is getting the best possible care, find out how to get the ideal health checkup package for your teenager.

CONCLUSION

The study found that Life skills therefore play an important role in the promotion of mental well-being. The promotion of mental well-being contributes to our motivation to look after ourselves and others, the prevention of mental disorders and the prevention of health and behaviour problems. Life skills help adolescents make informed decisions, communicate effectively, develop coping and management skills to lead a healthy and productive life. Adolescent health encompasses changing transitions within multiple domains including the physical, social, emotional, cognitive and intellectual. The fast-paced development of these different domains can lead to phenomenal growth during this period. They are susceptible to several preventable and treatable health problems like early & unintended pregnancy, unsafe sex leading to STI/HIV/AIDS, nutritional disorders like malnutrition, anemia & overweight, alcohol, tobacco and drug abuse, mental health concerns, injuries & violence. Adolescents experience rapid physical, cognitive and

psychosocial growth. This affects how they feel, think, make decisions, and interact with the world around them.

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